

Cycloaddition of the Thiol Group to Schiff Base Systems

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Cycloaddition of arylidene-2-(aminothiazole IV, aminopyridine V) and arylidene-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine VI, with mercaptoacetic acid was attempted. It has been found that substituted 4-thiazolidones (X, XI and XII) can be obtained from the reaction of Schiff bases (IV, V and VI) with mercaptoacetic acid in dry benzene.

ALTHOUGH the addition of the thiol group to Schiff bases where subsequent cyclization is possible, as in the case of thiazolidone formation, has been well established in several investigations¹⁻⁴; comparatively few instances have been reported wherein a simple addition product (scheme 1, structure II) has been obtained².

Surrey¹ observed that the expected thiazolidone III, which was the usual type of product in other Schiff bases investigated was not obtained by the interaction of mercaptoacetic acid and benzalanthranilic acid. Rather, a substance resulted having the composition of the supposed intermediate II, which corresponded to a simple addition product of the thiol and Schiff base. The structure II for this addition product, although, not rigorously confirmed, seems quite reasonable, particularly in the light of other reactions involving Schiff bases⁵⁻⁷.

Several substituted 4-thiazolidones have been investigated by Surrey³ and Troutman and Long⁴, and are particularly interesting as local anesthetic and anti-convulsant agents. Owing to the latter potential medicinal importance of this class of compounds, this has led us to extend the interest in finding new and efficient routes to the synthesis of functionally substituted 4-thiazolidones.

We have recently shown⁸ that reactions of nitro-substituted arylidene-2-aminothiazoles with diazomethane afforded 1,2,3-triazolines. We now report the extension of these studies on the unsaturated center in

the hereby used Schiff bases (IV, V and VI) in the formation of new substituted 4-thiazolidones (X, XI and XII).

Arylidene-2-aminothiazoles and 2-aminopyridines were prepared by the interaction of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole or 2-aminopyridine with substituted aromatic aldehydes. The reaction proceeded smoothly in ethanol and in the presence of piperidine as a catalyst giving a quantitative yield of the corresponding Schiff bases (IV and V, cf. Table 1).

Arylidene-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine (VI) were prepared by the condensation of 10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazine with aromatic aldehydes in glacial acetic acid.

The action of mercaptoacetic acid on Schiff bases (IV, V and VI) was studied. The compounds obtained from this reaction were 4-thiazolidones (X, XI and XII) which are in agreement with the data given by Surrey^{1,3}. The reaction proceeded smoothly in dry benzene by stirring the reaction mixture over periods of time varying from $\frac{1}{2}$ an-hour to 3 hours.

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Scheme 2

Substituted 4-thiazolidones (X, XI and XII) have been identified by a combination of elemental and spectral (IR) analysis. The infrared of 4-thiazolidones (X and XI) are characterized by a band in the region of 1700-1695 cm^{-1} which is attributed to the stretching vibration of C=O group; whereby 4-thiazolidones XII, show well defined absorption band at 1695 cm^{-1} due to C=O group and -NH absorption band at 3450 cm^{-1} .⁹

Experimental

All melting points were uncorrected and were obtained on a Koffler electrically heated melting point apparatus. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Pye Unicam IR spectrophotometer, SP 200G, using KBr discs.

Arylidene-2-aminothiazoles (IV) and arylidene-2-aminopyridines (V): A mixture of equimolecular quantities of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole or 2-aminopyridine and aldehyde in 50 ml ethanol and 0.2 ml piperidine was refluxed for 2 hours. The reaction

mixture was then concentrated and the product which separated on cooling was filtered off at the pump. The product was crystallized from the proper solvent. The results are listed in Table 1.

Arylidene-10-(hydrazinoacetyl) phenothiazines (VI)
 A mixture of equimolecular quantities of 10-(hydrazinoacetyl)-phenothiazine and aldehyde in 50 ml glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was poured, after cooling, in 300 ml of cold water where a solid mass was separated. The product was filtered off, washed with cold water and then crystallized from the proper solvent. The results are listed in Table 1.

4-Thiazolidones (X), (XI) and (XII): 0.06 mole of mercaptoacetic acid was added to a well stirred solution of 0.05 mole of Schiff base in 75 ml of dry benzene. The mixture was stirred over periods of time varying from $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour to 3 hours. The product which precipitated was filtered off and crystallized from the proper solvent. The results are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ARYLIDENE-2-(AMINOTHIAZOLE IV, AMINOPYRIDINE V) AND ARYLIDENE-10-(HYDRAZINOACETYL) PHENOTHIAZINE VI.

Compound No.	X	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analytical data					
					Calculated %			Observed %		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
IVa	OCH ₃	132-3	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO	69.39	4.76	9.52	69.45	4.55	9.76
b	o-OH	120-2	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ SO	68.57	4.29	10.00	68.33	4.05	10.25
c	N(CH ₃) ₂	95-8	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	70.36	5.54	13.68	70.05	5.33	13.59
d	m-NO ₂	113-4	75	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	62.14	3.56	13.59	62.32	3.69	13.70
e	p-NO ₂	15-5	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	62.14	3.56	13.59	62.05	3.73	13.45
Va	H	103-5	65	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂	79.12	5.49	15.38	79.00	5.35	15.15
b	OCH ₃	95-8	68	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	73.58	5.66	13.21	73.35	5.45	12.98
c	o-OH	66	92	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	72.73	5.05	14.14	72.67	4.95	14.06
d	N(CH ₃) ₂	73	93	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂	74.67	6.67	18.67	74.55	6.59	18.55
e	o-NO ₂	124-5	65	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂	63.44	3.96	18.50	63.39	3.88	18.35
f	m-NO ₂	105-7	68	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂	63.44	3.96	18.05	63.35	3.78	18.39
VIa	OCH ₃	175	65	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ SO ₂	67.87	4.83	10.79	67.75	4.72	10.67
b	o-OH	170	68	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ SO ₂	67.20	4.53	11.20	66.88	4.45	11.05
c	p-OH	173-4	70	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO ₂	67.20	4.53	11.20	67.33	4.62	11.25
d	N(CH ₃) ₂	169	75	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ SO ₂	68.66	5.47	13.93	68.51	5.33	13.81
e	p-NO ₂	147-8	63	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO ₂	62.38	3.96	13.86	62.25	3.85	13.71
f	C ₆ H ₄ -Fe-C ₅ H ₅	195-6	60	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₂ SO ₂ Fe	64.24	4.50	8.99	64.05	4.35	8.76

TABLE 2—4-THIAZOLIDONES (X, XI AND XII) DERIVED FROM SCHIFF BASES IV, V AND VI RESPECTIVELY.

Compound No.	X	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analytical data							
					Calculated %				Observed %			
					C	H	N	S	C	H	N	S
Xa	OCH ₃	166-7	45	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	61.96	4.35	7.61	17.39	61.88	4.25	7.48	17.28
b	o-OH	209	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	61.02	3.95	7.91	18.08	60.85	3.75	7.79	17.94
c	N(CH ₃) ₂	188	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O	62.99	4.99	11.02	16.80	62.78	4.85	10.87	16.70
d	m-NO ₂	175-6	35	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	56.40	3.39	10.97	16.71	56.31	3.28	10.88	16.66
e	p-NO ₂	163-4	35	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	56.40	3.39	10.97	16.71	56.35	3.45	11.06	16.69
XIa	H	98-9	35	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ SO	65.63	4.69	10.94	12.50	65.45	4.51	10.82	12.35
b	OCH ₃	117-8	35	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO ₂	62.94	4.90	9.79	11.19	62.82	4.75	9.65	11.00
c	o-OH	45	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ SO	61.76	4.41	10.29	11.76	61.62	4.62	10.32	11.82
d	N(CH ₃) ₂	61-3	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ SO	64.21	5.69	14.05	10.70	64.12	5.72	13.95	10.61
e	o-NO ₂	140	43	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ SO ₂	55.81	3.65	13.95	10.63	55.73	3.57	13.82	10.52
f	m-NO ₂	153	45	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ SO ₂	55.81	3.65	13.95	10.63	55.92	3.59	13.88	10.72
XIIa	OCH ₃	183-4	25	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	62.20	5.54	9.07	13.82	62.02	5.72	8.89	13.75
b	o-OH	182-3	22	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	61.47	4.23	9.35	14.25	61.22	4.12	9.15	14.09
c	p-OH	184-5	25	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	61.47	4.23	9.35	14.25	61.35	4.32	9.25	14.28
d	N(CH ₃) ₂	180-1	32	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	63.03	5.04	11.76	13.45	62.85	5.15	11.69	13.39
e	p-NO ₂	137-8	20	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	57.74	3.77	11.72	13.39	57.69	3.68	11.69	13.46
f	C ₆ H ₄ -Fe-C ₅ H ₅	185-6	20	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂ Fe	59.89	4.25	7.76	11.83	60.11	4.32	7.68	11.89

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